

Interaction Information Versus Movement Information in Free Particle Quantum Mechanics 2

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Oct. 18, 2024

In Part I, we argued that a particle with constant p, v moves as $x=vt$ both classically and quantum mechanically and both relativistically and nonrelativistically. We argued, however, that such smoothness in x (equal time in each constant dx) need not apply to p (momentum) which is proportional to impulse hits regardless what type of force is present. In fact, even though p is the same at each x , there is a probability associated with p given by $\exp(ipx)$, i.e. resolution pockets of size \hbar/p exist which have physical implications on interactions with classical objects such as a 2-slit apparatus. In other words, $\exp(ipx)$ describes interactions in a probabilistic way in space.

This then suggests that an interaction with a potential $V(x)$ must be affected by such probability. In Newtonian mechanics, a particle moves smoothly in dx with a $v(x)$, but then undergoes a second order change in $v(x)$ due to the force $F(x)$ in dx . Here, the interaction with p occurs in space in an unusual manner according to $\exp(ipx)$, so one would assume that $V(x)\exp(ipx)$ is the potential energy in space associated with this p in space probability. In other words, it is irrelevant that $x=vt$ for a constant p , one is interested in p interacting with $V(x)$. This is governed by $\exp(ipx)$.

As a result, one might consider a $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and describe the interaction as $W(x)V(x)$. Now, interaction with $\exp(ipx)$ occurs probabilistically in space, but the average energy E holds at all x points just as p holds at all x points for $\exp(ipx)$ and $pp/2m$ as well. Even though $pp/2m$ holds at each x point for $\exp(ipx)$, one cannot simply consider $a(p)pp/2m$ as describing the kinetic energy in \hbar/p because $\exp(ipx)$ is describing an interaction with impulse p in space in a probabilistic way and the $pp/2m$ energy linked to $V(x)\exp(ipx)$ should be linked to $pp/2m \exp(ipx)$ or $a(p)pp/2m \exp(ipx)$ when one considers the weight $a(p)$. The fact that $pp/2m$ is the same for all for $\exp(ipx)$ explains why it appears as $pp/2m$, i.e. with no x dependence. In other words, $pp/2m \exp(ipx)$ is a kind of dynamic interaction average kinetic energy.

The weighting $a(p)$ must be such that $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} + V(x) W = E W(x)$, i.e. E is a constant energy sitting with $W(x)$ like $V(x)$ with $W(x)$ except that $V(x)$ depends on x . This means that each $\exp(ipx)$ is associated with the same overall energy E .

We argued in Part 1, that $W^*(x)W(x)$ represents an average classical density which contains the physical effects of the $\exp(ipx)$ interaction probability in space. Thus, $EW(x)$ may be multiplied by $W^*(x)$ so that $E W^*(x)W(x) = E$ spatial density. Likewise $V(x)W^*W$ represents $V(x)$ multiplied by classical average density demonstrating the $\exp(ipx)$ interaction probabilities in space. As a result, $W^* (-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx}) = W^*W (-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W)$ so the term in () is an average kinetic energy at x , i.e. a conditional probability.

Interaction Probability in Space

We argued in Part I that even though $x=vt$ implies smooth motion in space, i.e the same dt in each constant dx relativistically or nonrelativistically and classical or quantum mechanically, the

interaction (impulse) based on p , momentum, with any type of force, need not follow this smooth probability. In fact, we argued that it follows $\exp(ipx)$ which is a complex probability. This describes how p interacts in space with objects such as a classical 2-slit apparatus. There is nothing quantum mechanical about the 2-slit apparatus, we argue, it is the probabilistic manner in which p interacts with it through $\exp(ipx)$. This probability in space exists even though p and $pp/2m$ are constant for any x . In other words, it is not enough to state that one has p at x as in a target collision. Dynamically, $\exp(ipx)$ describes how this p interacts.

The question then becomes: If $\exp(ipx)$ is the probability during an interaction, how does one justify using it to calculate averages such as $\sum_p a(p) f(p) \exp(ipx) / \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$?

To try to answer this question, we consider an interaction with a potential $V(x)$ taken from classical physics. Given that a 2-slit apparatus is completely classical, we suggest that a priori there is no particular reason why one cannot use the classical $V(x)$ potential. The point, however, we make is that the interaction with such a potential for a constant p is given by $\exp(ipx)$ over a wavelength. In other words, there is a spatial probability within \hbar/p and then this probability is repeated over the next \hbar/p units. In other words,

$V(x) \exp(ipx) =$ potential energy because the interaction of p with $V(x)$ is governed by the probability $\exp(ipx)$ ((1))

Now, $pp/2m$ is a constant for all x irrelevant of $\exp(ipx)$. $\exp(ipx)$ demonstrates the interaction of p with a classical potential e.g. $V(x)$ or a 2-slit apparatus. One might then be tempted to suggest that kinetic energy is $pp/2m$ at each x , but if one uses $V(x) \exp(ipx)$, where $V(x)$ is a potential energy, this must be balanced with $pp/2m \exp(ipx)$ because even though $pp/2m$ is the constant value at x , there is now a probability involved in the interaction and $pp/2m$ is associated with this probability. Thus, $pp/2m \exp(ipx)$ is a dynamic probability, not due to $x=vt$, but due to the $\exp(ipx)$ dynamism of the p interaction in space, versus $pp/2m$ being a static one which is completely detached from the interaction of p with $V(x)$.

One may next consider various $\exp(ipx)$ with weights, i.e.

$$W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((2))$$

Then: $\sum_p a(p) pp/2m \exp(ipx) + V(x) W(x)$ should give the energy together with the average interaction i.e. $E W(x)$ i.e.

$$-1/2m d/dx dW/dx + V(x) W(x) = E W(x) \quad ((3))$$

This is consistent with $W(x)$ being associated with $V(x)$. At the same time $pp/2$ being associated with $\exp(ipx)$ means that E is also associated with each $\exp(ipx)$ i.e.

$$a(p) \exp(ipx) pp/2m + \sum_k V_k a(p-k) \exp(ipx) = E a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{Here we have written: } V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx) \quad ((5))$$

Conditional Probability

In Part 1, we suggested that $W^*(x)W(x)$ equals a kind of average classical density which contains the effects of the $\exp(ipx)$ momentum spatial probability. If that is the case, then one may multiply ((3)) by $W^*(x)$. The first term then becomes:

$$-1/2m W^* d/dx dW/dx = -1/2m W^*W (d/dx dW/dx / W) \quad ((6))$$

If W^*W is a classical type of probability (which encompasses $\exp(ipx)$, the probability in space of a p interaction), then $d/dx dW/dx / W$ seems to have the form of a conditional probability.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argued in Part I that even though $x=vt$ implies smooth motion in space, an impulse interaction (which occurs for any kind of force) need not. In fact, we argued that $\exp(ipx)$ represents the spatial probability involved in such an interaction of p with a classical object such as a 2-slit apparatus or $V(x)$. Even though p or $pp/2m$ have the same value at each x , $\exp(ipx)$ is needed to describe the interaction in space.

This begs the question: Why should one use the average: $\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) f(p)\exp(ipx) / \text{sum over } a(p) \exp(ipx)$. We try to consider this by examining an interaction with $V(x)$. Given that an interaction occurs with a p constant, one immediately has $\exp(ipx)$ governing spatial probability in this interaction or $V(x)\exp(ipx)$ being the potential energy in probabilistic sense because the interaction necessarily involves this spatial probability. Even though $pp/2m$ is constant at each x , one is considering an interaction occurring with $V(x)$ and if $V(x)\exp(ipx)$ is probabilistic energy, then $pp/2m \exp(ipx)$ should be considered along with it. In other words one has a kind of dynamic $pp/2m \exp(ipx)$ kinetic energy. If one considers $W(x)=\text{Sum over } a(p)\exp(ipx)$, then one should have for dynamical energy:

$$\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)pp/2m \exp(ipx) + V(x) W(x) \text{ and this should equal } E W(x) \quad ((B))$$

because one multiplies energies by $\exp(ipx)$ s above. This means that for each $\exp(ipx)$: $a(p)pp/2m + \text{Sum over } k \text{ } V_k a(p-k) = a(p)E$ as discussed above.

In Part I, we suggested that W^*W is a classical style probability density in x , albeit one which shows $\exp(ipx)$ behaviour, then one may multiply ((B)) by W^* . This implies that $-1/2m d/dx dW/dx / W$ is a conditional probability.